

doi:10.5281/zenodo.15777086

The United Nations And Peacekeeping In The Democratic Republic Of Congo, 2010-2024

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ABSTRACT

This paper examines the role of United Nations peacekeeping in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC) from 2010 to 2024. Since gaining independence in 1960, the DRC has experienced persistent conflict driven by economic marginalization, political instability, and the proliferation of armed groups seeking survival through resource exploitation. This paper critically analyzes the ongoing crisis, focusing on how armed groups exacerbate instability and evaluating the effectiveness of UN peacekeeping efforts. Grounded in liberal institutionalism theory, the paper explores how economic deprivation fuels violence and the ways international institutions, particularly the UN, have attempted to mitigate the crisis. Employing a descriptive research design and secondary data, the paper assesses both the achievements and challenges faced by UN peacekeeping operations during this period. Despite efforts to stabilize the region, the persistence of armed groups, weak governance, and illicit resource exploitation continue to undermine peace efforts. The findings support the notion that armed groups sustain conflict for economic gains, perpetuating cycles of violence. The paper emphasizes the importance of inclusive national dialogue, governance reforms, a comprehensive approach integrating political, economic, and security reforms is essential for sustainable peace. This paper offers key insights for improving UN peacekeeping strategies and fostering long-term stability in the DRC.

Keywords: Armed groups, conflict resolution, Democratic Republic of Congo, governance, peace-building, resource exploitation, UN peacekeeping

INTRODUCTION

The establishment of mechanisms for the maintenance of international peace and security has consistently emerged as a struggle in the aftermath of significant conflicts between and within nation states in the international system. Kapur (2015), explains that the field of peacekeeping has undergone a significant transformation in the past years as it has transitioned swiftly from its conventional, predominantly military approach of monitoring ceasefires and establishing separation of forces following inter-state conflicts to a more sophisticated model that integrates a multitude of components. This modern approach involves collaborative efforts from military forces, institutions and nations, aiming to achieve and maintain peace in the precarious aftermath of conflicts. As we explore the foundations of international efforts to maintain peace, it is insightful to reflect on the League of Nations, an early 20th-century institution that played a pioneering role in shaping these concepts.

Following the outbreak of World War I, spanning from 1914 to 1918, the League of Nations was established on January 10, 1920, and fully commenced operations officially in November, 1920, following the League's first General Assembly, where all member states were represented in Geneva,

Switzerland. The organization, recognizing the profound impacts the war had on nations directly or indirectly, sought to address ongoing disputes and avert the reoccurrence of global conflicts. This predecessor to the United Nations Organization (UN) made attempts to foster collective security and international cooperation between nation states for a period of time. The League recorded some victories during its existence, some of which include the settlement of the Aaland Islands dispute between Sweden and Finland in 1920 that was resolved in Finland's favour. In 1920, the League also settled the border clash between Yugoslavia and Albania when it persuaded Yugoslavia to withdraw its troops from Albania. It also rendered economic assistance to countries such as Austria and Hungary that suffered devastating consequences as a result of the war.

Despite its noble objectives and achievements recorded, the League of Nations faced considerable challenges such as lack of willingness of its member states to make financial and military contributions to achieve the organization's main objective of avoiding the outbreak of wars. Also, the absence of key global players like the United States of America (USA) and a limited mandate hindered its effectiveness. The League operated on a fragile peace that could not prevent the outbreak of World War II. This highlighted the need for a more comprehensive and robust international organization dedicated to maintaining global peace.

Following the events of the Second World War (WWII), the United Nations was founded on October 24, 1945 by fifty one (51) countries. Just like the First World War served as a catalyst for the establishment of the League of Nations, the Second World War similarly prompted the formation of a much resilient international organization, the United Nations, dedicated to the preservation of global peace through the prevention, management and resolution of conflicts. (Kapur, 2015).

Though the prevention, management and resolution of conflicts is the responsibility of individual states to bear, Satish Nambiar explains in his journal article, 'United Nations Peacekeeping Operations', that the primary responsibility of upholding international peace and security lies with the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) as mandated by the United Nations Charter. In fulfilling this mandate, according to the UN official website, the United Nations Department of Peace Operations (DPO), formerly known as the Department of Peacekeeping Operations (DPKO) was created in 1992, during the tenure of Boutros-Ghali. Since its inception, the department has evolved into an indispensable tool for the management of the ever-evolving conflicts that jeopardize world peace and security.

For over 75 years, UN Peacekeeping has served as a vital instrument in mitigating conflicts and fostering global peace and security. The United Nations, as stated on its official website, elucidates that the UN Peacekeepers carry out their operations in areas of extreme tension and conflict with the aim of protecting the lives and property of civilians. The roles of the peacekeepers also involve assisting countries navigate the difficult path from conflict to peace, facilitation of the implementation of peace agreements, ensuring stability in conflict-ridden zones, strengthening the rule of law and the establishment of civic and social conditions necessary for peace.

Peacekeepers are also saddled with the responsibility of strengthening local, regional and national institutions to address the causes of conflict such as discrimination, inequality and marginalization. This responsibility, also known as 'peace support' in contemporary peacekeeping involves the coordinated presence of the UN military, police, and civilian personnel, who undertake a wide range of tasks including humanitarian assistance, policing, human rights and electoral monitoring, social and economic rehabilitation and reconstruction as well as working cohesively with local stakeholders to mitigate and manage local conflicts (Woodhouse, *et al.*, 2008).

Despite operational imperfections, several comparative studies have shown that peacekeeping operations are instrumental in the protection of civilian lives, promotion of human rights, lowering levels of violence and casualties, mitigation of the devastating consequences of the outbreak of wars as well as higher prospects of peace in the aftermath of the conflicts (Klobucista and Ferragamo, 2023).

The UN Peacekeeping Operations in Africa have a rich and complex history, as it dates back to the late 1990s, when the United Nations Security Council (UNSC) launched a series of peacekeeping operations in Africa aimed at resolving civil wars through the management of conflicts, facilitation of peace processes and maintenance of stability across the region (Gowan and Forti, 2023). Approximately 50% of

all UN Peacekeeping Operations have been carried out on the African continent, including missions in Rwanda, Sierra Leone, Burundi, the Democratic Republic of Congo, Sudan and South Sudan, Mali, Central African Republic, etc. As at 2016, nine (9) out of the sixteen (16) active UN Peacekeeping operations were in Africa (Rettig, 2016). By 2023, Africa had hosted over 30 UN Peacekeeping Operations, surpassing any other region in the number of such operations conducted (Klobucista and Ferragamo, 2023).

The dynamics of peacekeeping in Africa has evolved over the years and have played a pivotal role in addressing conflicts, maintaining peace and promoting stability across the continent. Overtime, the involvement of the UN has expanded, marking the emergence of numerous peacekeeping initiatives from the United Nations Organization Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo (MONUC), UN's first peacekeeping operation in Africa, established in 1960 to address the crisis following the Congo's declaration of independence from Belgium to operation such as the UN Transition Assistance Group (UNTAG) overseeing Namibia's independence and interventions in South Africa's anti-apartheid struggle. Also worthy of note are the immense challenges faced by the Department of Peacekeeping Operations (DPKO) in the 1990s during the Rwandan genocide and the crisis in Somalia, underscoring the complexities and limitations of peacekeeping efforts which prompted a reevaluation of strategies and reforms within UN peacekeeping efforts.

UN peacekeeping operations in Africa have a long and complex history, marked by significant challenges and varied outcomes. Since the late 1990s and through the 2000s to the present day, UN Peacekeeping operations in Africa have encountered increasingly intricate challenges. Some of these challenges include shortages in financial and human resources, insufficient coordination, complex operational mandates, the presence of insurgencies, terrorist organizations, and hostile communities. These challenges have been particularly pronounced in the Democratic Republic of Congo, Sierra Leone, Liberia, Sudan, Mali, Central African Republic and various other states on the continent.

A critical analysis of a selected case study is suitable in order to uncover the complex nature of African conflicts, which have often hindered the effectiveness of UN interventions. This study seeks to examine the challenges of peacekeeping in order to understand why UN peace efforts in Africa have frequently yielded minimal results, identify key lessons learned, and offer recommendations for improving future operations.

This research focuses on the United Nations and its peacekeeping efforts in the Democratic Republic of Congo from 2010 to 2024. It explores the various challenges and achievements of the organization in their attempt to restore stability, protect civilians, and support the Congolese government in addressing the causes of conflict.

The deep-rooted instability in the Democratic Republic of Congo can be traced back to historical and geopolitical influences, particularly Belgium's colonial rule and continued post-independence involvement, which left behind weak institutions and political fragmentation. Additionally, Cold War rivalries saw the former Soviet Union and the United States supporting various factions, further fueling divisions and complicating efforts to establish lasting peace. These historical factors, alongside other factors such as armed conflict, human rights violations, political instability, and humanitarian violations have contributed to the persistent challenges that undermine peace and stability in the region, making the UN's decades-long peacekeeping operations in the country an ongoing struggle to restore regional peace and security.

Despite its long-term presence in the region and resources dedicated to the operation, the UN peacekeeping efforts is often criticized for its limited success in achieving sustainable peace and stability in the region.

In subsequent chapters, this case study will examine the causes of the conflict leading to the intervention of the United Nations in the Democratic Republic of Congo. It will also delve into the specific challenges and complexities of its peacekeeping operations. By exploring these dynamics in greater detail, the study aims to identify lessons learned provide valuable recommendations for strengthening future UN peace operations.

Based on the above, the following objectives are advanced for interrogation:

1. Identify the causes of the conflict in the Democratic Republic of Congo.
2. Ascertain the lessons learned from the UN Operations in DR Congo.

THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

Liberal Institutionalism, also known as Liberal Internationalism or Liberalism in International Relations, is adopted as a theoretical framework. It emphasizes the role of international institutions, cooperation, and diplomacy in shaping world politics. This theory postulates that regional and international institutions play fundamental roles in facilitating cooperation and peace between nation-states (Johnson and Heiss, 2018). Liberal institutionalism posits that achieving peace in international affairs requires states to collaborate and, consequently, relinquish a portion of their sovereignty to establish 'integrated communities'. This approach aims to foster economic growth and address regional and global security concerns (Caporaso & Jupille, 1999). Within a liberal institutionalism model, states collaboratively seek to maximize absolute gains through cooperation (Devitt, 2011). Hence, through its emphasis on international organizations like the United Nations, liberal institutionalism advocates for an increased focus on soft power and cooperation among member states.

For a comprehensive understanding of the viewpoint advocated by supporters of liberal institutionalism, it is essential to have a clear understanding of Liberalism. Liberalism is considered the broader ideological and philosophical foundation that provides the groundwork for liberal institutionalism. Liberalism, as a political and economic philosophy, emphasizes individual rights, liberty, democracy, and the rule of law. In the context of international relations, liberalism values institutions and considers them as autonomous players in shaping global politics (Toksöz, 2017). This means that international and regional organizations such as the United Nations, World Bank, International Monetary Fund (IMF), the African Union (AU), the European Union (EU), wield significant influence and possess decision-making power independently of individual countries. They can set agendas, make policies, and implement initiatives that impact global affairs, sometimes even exerting pressure on member states to comply with their directives. Duguri *et al.* explain in their 2021 work, 'International Relations, Realism, and Liberalism: A Theoretical Review', that Liberalism comprises a diverse array of ideas and perspectives concerning how institutions, behaviors, and economic relationships can constrain and alleviate state violence. On this backdrop, the primary focus of liberalism is to establish regional and international institutions aimed at safeguarding the freedom of less powerful states by curbing and monitoring the political influence of all states, particularly the more dominant ones (Duguri *et al.*, 2021). Liberal institutionalism, as a theory of international relations, builds upon these liberal principles but focuses more narrowly on the role of international institutions and cooperation among states.

Liberal institutionalism emerged as a reaction to the pessimism and power-centric focus of realism and a corrective to this traditional international relations theory, challenging the notion that powerful nation-states dictate global politics while considering international institutions as inconsequential. Realism contends that states within the international system are primarily focused on advancing their selfish interests, even if it comes at the expense of other states. According to Johnson and Heiss (2018), realism suggests that in the world of international relations, nation-states are rational actors who act independently in a system without a higher authority, making strategic decisions to achieve their goals. Realists are also of the opinion that accumulating power is crucial for a country's survival and success, highlighting the competitive aspect of global politics. In realist thinking, when one state gains, another loses, illustrating a zero-sum view of international relations.

On the contrary, Liberal Institutionalism suggests that states can attain lasting cooperation by associating themselves with regional and international institutions such as the United Nations. Liberal Institutionalism rejects the realist notion that global politics is a power struggle, with military security issues taking precedence. Instead, it proposes that we can 'imagine a world in which actors other than states participate directly in world politics, in which a clear hierarchy of issues does not exist, and in which force is an ineffective instrument of policy (Baylis & Smith, 2005).

Liberal Institutionalism came into limelight in the 18th Century, with its roots embedded in significant historical events and advancements. In 1795, Immanuel Kant, a political philosopher, laid the groundwork

for sustainable international cooperation in his essay, 'Perpetual Peace' (Johnson and Heiss, 2018). Following the demise of World War I (WWI), the League of Nations was established, serving as a precursor to the United Nations. Woodrow Wilson, the then President of the United States, played a pivotal role in advocating for a league aimed at preventing future conflicts through global collaboration and diplomacy. Kant's concepts for achieving lasting cooperation were later incorporated into the Fourteen Points agenda by Woodrow Wilson after WWI, leading to the creation of the League of Nations, the initial international organization where nations joined forces to pursue shared interests.

In his 1939 work "The Twenty Years' Crisis," E.H. Carr criticized those who believed in the possibility of transnational connections or international institutions to counteract the inherent tendencies of states toward power, competition, and armed conflict. While acknowledging the normative appeal of Liberalism, Carr contended that, in the current landscape of competing nation-states, the realist paradigm was a more effective guide and predictor of political behavior. Towards the end of 1939, the fragile peace which had existed after WWI was disrupted and World War II (WWII) broke out, following Hitler's invasion of Poland. This led to the demise of the League of Nations, as the aim of its establishment, to end future wars, had been defeated. Liberalism was threatened after the failure of the League of Nations to foster cooperation among states within the international system. The outbreak of the Second World War in September, 1939 further reinforced Carr's assertions.

The end of World War II (WW2) led to the establishment of the United Nations in 1945, rekindling prospects for global order through international collaboration and the participation of states in international organizations. The UN Charter further reinforced liberal principles, emphasizing the promotion of international cooperation, respect for human rights, and the peaceful resolution of disputes.

Since its inception, liberal ideas have continued to encounter persistent challenges, primarily due to the recurring outbreak of wars in several regions on the global stage and the hesitancy of some states to cede a portion of their authority to international organizations. These challenges have sparked debates and scholarly inquiries into the efficacy of liberal principles in maintaining global order.

Political scholars Nye and Keohane contributed significantly to this discourse. The modern articulation of liberal institutionalism gained prominence with the publication of their book "Power and Interdependence" in 1977. Keohane and Nye (1977) argue that international institutions and interdependence could influence state behavior and promote cooperation, challenging the realist emphasis on power politics. They explained that international institutions, when structured with liberal principles, could serve as effective mechanisms for promoting peace, cooperation, and the management and resolution of conflicts among states. According to their analysis, these institutions play a crucial role in managing power relations, reducing the likelihood of war, and fostering mutual understanding.

Liberal institutionalism posits that international institutions, such as the UN, can play a pivotal role in preventing conflicts, promoting cooperation, and fostering stability. The theory provides a theoretical framework that aligns closely with the principles and functions of the United Nations. The UN serves as a practical manifestation of liberal ideas in international relations, working to foster cooperation, prevent conflicts, protect human rights, and promote a rule-based international order. Despite the challenges and criticisms faced by the UN, its institutional structure reflects a commitment to liberal ideals and the belief in the efficacy of international cooperation for addressing global issues.

Applying Liberal Institutionalism to this study provides a lens to understand the principles backing the establishment of MONUSCO in the Democratic Republic of Congo. It highlights how the UN peacekeeping operations are deployed to work towards reducing violence, protecting civilians, and supporting political processes in a country marred by decades of conflict and instability, internal strife, regional tensions, rise of armed groups and human rights abuses. Liberal Institutionalism emphasizes the importance of multilateral cooperation among states in addressing the complex and multifaceted issues in conflicted regions. This involves the contribution of troops, financial and human resources to peacekeeping operations.

Liberal Institutionalism places a strong emphasis on conflict resolution through diplomacy (Keohane and Nye 1977). In other words, peacekeeping in the UN and other organizations generally involve diplomatic efforts to bring conflicting parties to the negotiating table. These organizations provide platforms for

dialogue, mediation, and establishment of agreements, contributing to the resolution of disputes and the prevention of further violence.

The establishment of institutional frameworks is also a crucial aspect in liberal institutionalism. In DR Congo, MONUSCO for example, serves as an institutional framework designed to address and handle the causes of conflict, support the political processes, facilitate cooperation and interaction and promote socio-economic development. Institutional structures such as MONUSCO, aim to create sustainable conditions for peace and stability within conflict-ridden regions.

Liberal Institutionalism assumes that international institutions can effectively address conflicts brewing up on the global scene, threatening global peace and security. However, The UN peacekeeping operation in DR Congo has faced numerous challenges that impact the fundamental tenets of liberal institutionalism. Such issues include the complexities of the conflict as it involves numerous armed groups, clashing interests of contributing states, complex historical grievances, etc. All these intricacies have made it difficult to develop sustainable solutions to the conflict in DR Congo, hence, undermining the liberal institutionalism credence in the power of international cooperation and highlighting the need for the adoption of the frustration-aggression theory in understanding the details behind the delayed successes of the United Nations peace operations.

In conclusion, liberal institutionalism, a theoretical framework in international relations, emphasizes on the role of international institutions, cooperation, and diplomacy in maintaining global peace and order. This perspective sees institutions like the United Nations (UN) as crucial for promoting stability and mitigating conflicts. The relationship between liberal institutionalism and the United Nations is symbiotic; with liberal institutionalism providing a theoretical foundation for the UN's existence by emphasizing the importance of international cooperation, and collective security, thereby legitimizing and reinforcing the UN's role in global governance and the organization serving as a practical manifestation of liberal principles in international relations. The UN, as an embodiment of these liberal institutionalist principles, engages in peacekeeping operations around the world in pursuance of global peace and stability such as its operation in the DR Congo, MONUSCO which is the case study for this thesis. Despite the constraints faced by the UN in fulfilling its role of maintaining global peace as an international institution such as resource constraints, clashing interests of contributing states, complex history of conflicts, numerous stakeholders in conflicts etc., the UN remains a central player in the liberal institutionalist vision for global governance, showcasing both the potential and limitations of international institutions in addressing complex conflicts and promoting global peace and security.

UNDERSTANDING THE CAUSES OF CONFLICT IN THE DEMOCRATIC REPUBLIC OF CONGO

Historical Grievances and Colonial Legacy: The Democratic Republic of Congo, formerly known as Zaire, is one of the largest countries in Africa, encompassing a landmass of 2.38 million square kilometers. Despite its vast size, the country is sparsely populated, ranking the 20th least densely populated country on the continent (Ayodele, 2017). It is a country richly endowed with natural resources ranging from minerals to forestry, water and fertile agricultural land, being a leading exporter of copper and cobalt in the international market. Ironically, despite the abundance of natural resources, the country is home to some of the world's poorest people. According to the UN Environment Programme, the intense demand for minerals has led to challenges such as environmental degradation and fueled violent conflict, which in turn has contributed to a prolonged humanitarian crisis. The country has a chaotic history scarred by colonization, pre-independence struggle, post-independence political instability, repeated conflicts and the continuous rise of rebel groups that frequently revolt against the government.

Like every other African country, DR Congo quickly became a prey in the hands of colonial exploitation. Following the Berlin Conference of 1884-1885, during which European powers negotiated and laid claims to the African territory, DR Congo became the territory of Belgium under King Leopold (Campbell, 2008). During the era of colonization, the country was continually stripped of its wealth by the Belgian colonizers. Blessed with resources such as copper, gold, lithium, rubber, and palm oil, the exploitation of these assets for the benefit of the Belgian economy led to significant economic and social

impacts on the region. Exclusive mining rights in Katanga were granted to the Belgian business Union Minière du Haut Katanga in 1906 and remained that way until 1999 (Gordon, 1962). Although Belgian colonialism in the country was harsh, it wasn't until the latter part of the 1950s that local opposition began to mature among the Congolese.

Political Instability and Weak Governance: In the 1950s and 1960s, many African countries began agitating for freedom from colonial rule and independence, the Congo was no exception. The push for independence was fraught with challenges, including resistance from the colonial powers and complex tribal politics among the various ethnic groups within the country. However, Congo eventually gained its independence on June 30th, 1960. Soon after the post-independence celebrations, the country descended into turmoil, leading to one of the world's most complex conflicts (Seybolt, 2000). The crisis resulted from a combination of factors including decolonization movements in Africa, Cold War politics, and secessionist movements by the provinces of Katanga and South Kasai, foreign interventions and internal political struggles between factions and their leaders.

Despite independence and the end of Belgian direct rule in the country, the problem of unwanted foreign presence and activities did not immediately come to a halt (Aksu, 2003). Aksu further explains that the Belgian government maintained a large army and police force to control its former colony due to the country's vastness as claimed, but primarily driven by the need to protect its strategic interests in the country's mineral wealth. Within the army, the Congolese were limited to roles such as privates and constables, with only a few non-commissioned officers among them and no locally trained officers. First, there was an internal struggle within the army. Congolese troops and policemen resisted the last Belgian foreigners still in power, igniting a mutiny that led to years of conflict and instability (Campbell, 2008). The newly independent nation also had to contend with internal political power struggles and secessionist aspirations, particularly in the mineral-rich province of Katanga, a region which declared independence under Moïse Tshombe's leadership with the support of the Belgian business interests, with the intention of retaining control over the province's significant mineral wealth, particularly its copper mines.

Prime Minister Patrice Lumumba, desperate for peace, sought assistance from the United Nations and the US, but received no substantial support. The UN dispatched a peacekeeping force but decided not to intervene in the Congolese government's conflict with the secessionists, as it was considered an internal conflict. In a final effort to stabilize the country, he turned to the Soviet Union for assistance. This action generated speculation and prompted international involvement, influenced by the broader context of the ongoing Cold war during that period. Western countries, alarmed by Lumumba's appeal to the Soviet Union, labeled him a communist, intensifying the geopolitical tensions surrounding Congo's crisis as relationships began to deteriorate including the relationship between Prime Minister Lumumba and President Joseph Kasavubu, the first president of the country. (BisiMedia, 2024).

In response to the Congo Crisis, the United Nations launched its first major peacekeeping operation in the country, ONUC (United Nations Operation in the Congo), spanning July 1960 to June 1964. According to official UN records, the operation, ONUC, was a significant landmark in the history of UN peacekeeping, as it involved a broader scope of responsibilities than any previous operation. Initially, the UN through ONUC, anticipated intervening in order to address an inter-state conflict emerging from the decolonization process, but soon found itself in the position of having to redefine the principles guiding its involvement in the crisis (Aksu, 2003). According to the UN in an official website, the operation aimed to assist the country by ensuring the withdrawal of Belgian forces, which were still significantly present in the country, and helping the central government with technical assistance. Subsequently, ONUC's mandate was expanded to include upholding the Congo's political freedom and territorial integrity, averting civil conflict, and ensuring the removal of all foreign mercenaries and paramilitary and advisory personnel not operating under the UN command. In total, the peacekeeping operation gulped a whopping \$400.1 million as expenditures as a result of assuming responsibilities which were beyond the initial mandate of the operation.

Lumumba was placed under house arrest with UN peacekeepers as his guards. He managed to escape with the assistance of his loyalists and fled towards the rebel-backed Stanleyville. Unfortunately, he was captured on December 1, 1960, and taken to the capital, Léopoldville. The Soviet Union petitioned the

UNSC for Lumumba's release and immediate restoration as Prime Minister. The petition was rejected with a vote of 8 against and 2 in favor. Following this resolution, Lumumba was transferred to Katanga, where he was tortured and transferred to Moïse Tshombe's forces, the leader of Pro-Western Katanga province. He was later executed on January 17, 1961. His assassination led to intense reactions both within and outside the country.

After his assassination, the conflict persisted; the warring factions still could not reconcile their differences. The battle to put an end to the secession of Katanga province continued as the re-appointed president Kasa-Vubu and Moïse Tshombe could not reach an agreement. As a result of the crisis, former UN Secretary-General Dag Hammarskjöld made a decision to visit the Congo to broker a cease-fire between the two factions. Unfortunately, the plane carrying Hammarskjöld and his delegates crashed, killing everyone on board.

Following the orders of Secretary-General U Thant, the successor of Hammarskjöld, the UN operation entered a new phase, as the peacekeeping force was bolstered, and the operation, according to the UN official website, reached a peak of nearly 20,000 UN officers in the Congo. Their mission was to protect the country from external interference, particularly by recapturing the mineral-rich Katanga, which had seceded under the leadership of Tshombe, evacuating foreign mercenaries from the province, and preventing clashes and civil unrest, using force as a last resort if necessary. The operation faced numerous challenges, including logistical difficulties, humanitarian crises, complex political dynamics, and resistance from various factions which led to its difficulty in accessing seceded provinces of Katanga and South Kasai.

The United Nations' intervention through ONUC played a crucial role in restoring relative peace and order, supporting the newly independent Congolese government, and preventing the Congo from becoming a flashpoint in the Cold War. Despite its challenges, ONUC successfully reunited the seceded regions and stabilized the Congo during a critical period in its history. However, the peace restored was precarious, as the causes of the crises- such as economic exploitation and control over natural resources by both internal and external forces- were not fully addressed.

After the departure of the UN operation ONUC in June 1964, the country continued to struggle with the same political instability. Elections were held in 1965 after the country had partially succeeded in suppressing rebellious groups. Due to political differences and ethnic tensions, a deadlock arose between Tshombe's party and President Kasa-Vubu. Instead of compromising, Kasa-Vubu dismissed Tshombe, who had returned as Prime Minister, and appointed Évariste Kimba. Again, history seemed to repeat itself.

In November 1965, former army leader and Chief of Staff of the Congolese army, Joseph-Désiré Mobutu who would later adopt the name Mobutu Sese Seko, took advantage of the political instability and launched a bloodless coup where he consolidated power for himself, promising to restore power to a democratically elected government within five years, a promise he never fulfilled (Amnesty International, 2024). He ruled Congo (which he renamed Zaire) with an iron fist, abolishing the office of the Prime Minister as well as the parliament and establishing a one-party state. He ruled for over three decades, from 1965 until 1997, when he was finally ousted.

After Mobutu's regime fell in 1997, there was a significant increase in armed factions at both local and regional levels as the state failed to deliver basic services or security. Widespread poverty and limited economic prospects drove many individuals into the ranks of these groups, deepening the country's instability (Amnesty International, 2024).

Regional Dynamics: According to Zapata (2011), the 1994 Rwandan Genocide was the trigger that set off the regional crisis during the time, drawing neighboring countries into the Congo crisis, which eventually resulted in the outbreak of the first Congo War (October 1996 – May 1997). For context, majority of the Rwandan population belonged to the Hutu tribe, but the Tutsi minority had long occupied leadership positions, had better access to education and other economic advantages. All that was reversed after the country gained its independence in 1962 when Hutus ceased political control, marginalizing the minority Tutsis. Following the death of the then President Juvenal Habyarimana, and his colleague, former President Cyprien Ntaryamira of Burundi, approximately 800,000 Tutsis and pro-peace Hutus

were slaughtered by the Hutu extremist government between April-July 1994, within a period of 100 days. The Rwandan Patriotic Front (RPF), a Tutsi-led rebel group led by Paul Kagame, ended the genocide by July 1994, defeating the Hutu government responsible for orchestrating the genocide.

During and after the genocide, over two million refugees including Hutu perpetrators of the genocide, fearing retribution, migrated to neighboring countries, including the already destabilized Congo (which was known as Zaire at the time), located at the western border of Rwanda. Refugee camps in Kivu, Eastern Congo, an area occupied by ethnic Tutsis, became bases for exiled refugees who terrorized the local population and used the region as a base from which to attack Rwanda. In October 1996, Eastern Congolese Tutsis in the Kivu region led an uprising under the rebel movement, the Congolese Rally for Democracy (RCD), to force the Rwandans out of Congo. This uprising eventually sparked what was later referred to as the First Congo War.

Bailey (2024), explains that the new pro-Tutsi Rwandan government, headed by Vice President Paul Kagame, along with Ugandan leader Yoweri Museveni, believed that Mobutu was not adequately addressing the violence that had been brewing in Eastern Zaire. Consequently, Rwanda and Uganda allied with the Alliance of Democratic Forces for the Liberation of the Congo (AFDL), an anti-Mobutu coalition controlled by Laurent-Désiré Kabila. On October 26, 1996, attributable to their interests in the country's rich natural resources, the combined forces invaded Zaire to take control and overthrow Mobutu. In six months, Mobutu was overthrown and exiled, eastern Zaire was stabilized, and Kabila assumed the position of the president of the renamed Democratic Republic of the Congo in September, 1997.

In 1998, the Second Congo War, otherwise known as the Great War of Africa, erupted and persisted for five years (Zapata, 2011). It began when Kabila failed to meet the expectations of his people and supporters in stabilizing Eastern Congo, allowing the Hutu rebellion to regroup there. In response, Uganda and Rwanda, who had previously supported Kabila, joined forces to invade Congo and depose him. Neighboring countries Angola, Namibia, and Zimbabwe then allied with Congo to defend Kabila and counter the Ugandan and Rwandan forces, dragging six (6) countries into the conflict. It is important to note that the interests of these countries in Congo's natural resources played a crucial role in fueling the conflict, as various factions sought to benefit from or gain some level of control on its mineral-rich regions (Williams, 2013).

The war officially ended with the signing of the Lusaka Ceasefire Agreement between the countries involved in the conflict, Congo, Angola, Namibia, Uganda, Rwanda and Zimbabwe. This was a critical step towards ending the conflict as it laid the groundwork for subsequent peace efforts, including establishment of the UN operation by the Security Council, MONUC (the United Nations Mission in the Democratic Republic of Congo) and the deployment of 5000 UN peacekeepers in July 1999 to monitor the ceasefire and facilitate the peace process intended to repress violence between rebel and pro-government factions (Zapata, 2011).

MONUC's mandate included overseeing the ceasefire, facilitating the disarmament, demobilization, and reintegration of combatants, and supporting the delivery of humanitarian aid. The operation played a crucial role in the promotion of human rights and protection of civilians, supporting the transitional government in its efforts to stabilize the country and the organization of democratic elections.

In January 2001, President of DR Congo, Laurent-Désiré Kabila was assassinated, and his son, Joseph Kabila, assumed the presidency. Joseph Kabila demonstrated strong negotiating skills and, in 2002, successfully brokered peace deals that led to the withdrawal of Rwandan and Ugandan forces from the Congo. In December 2002, he negotiated a peace agreement with internal rebel groups, promising a power-sharing interim government which promised to ensure stability and foster cooperation among diverse political actors while laying the groundwork for a more permanent and inclusive political solution. This agreement was formalized when Kabila signed a transitional constitution in April 2003, officially marking the end of the second Congo War.

Competition over Resources: Following the collapse of Mobutu Sese Seko's regime in May 1997, the Democratic Republic of Congo witnessed the rapid emergence of numerous armed factions vying for territorial and economic control (Amnesty International, 2024). These emerging armed groups leveraged on the state's failure to provide essential services and security to the population. The lack of economic

opportunities and development pushed many people to join armed groups, further destabilizing the country. The competition over the country's abundant mineral wealth has ever since, provided lucrative revenue streams for militias and their foreign illicit partners. Armed groups are able to finance their operations, purchase weapons, and pay combatants using revenue generated from illicit mining, mineral trafficking, ore taxation, smuggling, and artisanal extraction, sustaining armed groups such as M23 and FDLR (Lewis *et al.*, 2025). At the same time, growing international demand, particularly from electronics and jewelry manufacturers, has intensified the exploitation of these resources, as global supply chains remain poorly regulated (Callaway, 2017).

Weak-state institutions have also led to the establishment of pseudo-governments by these armed groups in various local areas which create enabling environments for them to operate with minimal or no restrictions, siphoning government revenues and undermining the state's capacity to deliver basic services and security. Armed groups take advantage of artisanal and small-scale mining (ASM) by recruiting workers, collecting taxes, and taking over mining sites. This often leads to violence and serious human rights abuses against local communities, including forced labor of women and children (Amnesty International, 2023). In addition, the fragmentation of armed groups into smaller, more agile groups has intensified competition, as each group seeks to secure control over these resources.

This scramble for resources continue to perpetuate cycles of violence and humanitarian abuse, undermining efforts to restore central governance and commence peace building efforts. As long as economic incentives for armed predation remain high and governance deficits persist, competition over resource control may continue to finance armed violence and obstruct pathways to peace in DR Congo as this issue has eaten deep into the country's fabric.

LESSONS LEARNED FROM THE UN OPERATIONS IN DR CONGO

The United Nations Peacekeeping Operation in DR Congo has been one of the largest and most complex peacekeeping operations undertaken by the UN. Since its inception, the UN has faced numerous challenges, including dealing with persistent armed conflict, protecting civilians, and addressing governance issues in a volatile and resource-rich country.

1 The Importance of Mandate Clarity: One of the key lessons learned from United Nations peacekeeping efforts in the Democratic Republic of the Congo is the critical importance of a clear, well-defined, and achievable mandate (Sarwar, 2007). Such a mandate is essential for setting focused goals and ensuring peacekeepers fully understand their mission, while also preventing an overly broad mandate that could stretch resources thin, hindering the operation's ability to perform effectively across all areas. MONUSCO's mandate was revised multiple times, leading to unnecessary financial costs that could have been avoided with a more clearly defined mandate from the outset.

2. Logistical Challenges: The vast and difficult terrain of the DR Congo posed significant logistical challenges for UN peace efforts in the country (Kimathi, *et al.*, 2024). The size and complexity of the conflict ridden regions also limited the mission's mobility and rapid response capabilities. For future operations, the UN is to take this into serious consideration, prioritizing investments in advanced technology, air mobility, and infrastructure improvements, enabling peacekeepers to respond more promptly and effectively to emerging threats.

3. Engagement with Local and Regional Actors: The study of peace efforts in the Democratic Republic of Congo underscores the critical importance of engaging regional and local stakeholders in peacekeeping operations. While the United Nations collaborated with non-governmental organizations (NGOs) to address various challenges, deeper and more sustained partnerships with local civil society, political actors, and neighboring states could have significantly improved the mission's effectiveness from an earlier stage. Limited engagement with grassroots organizations and regional governments resulted in poor information flow, a shallow understanding of the local conflict dynamics, and diminished community trust in the peacekeeping process. Kimathi *et al.* (2024) emphasize that one of the key lessons learned is the need to strengthen relationships with local communities through dialogue initiatives, outreach programs, and strategic partnerships with local leaders and civil society. Meaningful engagement

with regional and local actors is not only vital for the success of peacekeeping operations but also essential for ensuring their legitimacy and long-term sustainability.

4. Prioritizing Accountability: MONUSCO, like some other UN peacekeeping missions, faced allegations of misconduct, which severely damaged the credibility and legitimacy of the mission (Askin, 2016). Addressing this challenge is crucial for the success of future operations. The UN must continue to strengthen accountability mechanisms, provide training around this reoccurring challenge to peacekeepers, and ensure that disciplinary actions are taken immediately and openly against perpetrators to maintain the trust of local populations.

5. Holistic Approach to Peacekeeping Operations: Boutellis (2013) emphasizes that for UN peacekeeping to remain relevant, it must undergo meaningful reform. A key lesson from the UN's operations in the Democratic Republic of Congo is the necessity of adopting a comprehensive strategy—one that goes beyond military and security measures to include social, political, and economic dimensions. While military intervention may be essential for immediate stabilization, a narrow focus on security alone is insufficient to address the underlying causes of conflict or to establish lasting peace. Sustainable outcomes require an integrated approach that aligns security efforts with broader peacebuilding and development goals.

For example, even though the UN successfully neutralized M23 in 2013, the absence of a comprehensive economic development plan led to a failure in securing lasting stability. The continued lack of jobs, infrastructure, and essential services left many communities vulnerable, with armed groups able to regroup and exploit these gaps. Additionally, addressing governance and political issues, such as weak institutions and corruption, is crucial in preventing the recurrence of conflict.

A comprehensive plan would, therefore, involve integrating efforts across multiple sectors (security, governance, economic development, and civil society engagement) ensuring that the response to the conflict is holistic, sustainable, and long-term. This approach helps build resilience, reduces the likelihood of conflict re-emerging, and promotes a stable and thriving society.

These lessons offer valuable insights that can enhance the effectiveness of future UN peacekeeping operations, leading to greater success. By taking into consideration these experiences from the UN's peace operations in DR Congo, future operations can better navigate the complexities of conflict environments, improve their operational strategies, and ultimately achieve greater success in fostering peace and stability in affected regions.

CONCLUDING REMARKS

This study critically analyzes UN peacekeeping efforts in the Democratic Republic of Congo (DRC), a country long plagued by political instability, violence, and humanitarian crises rooted in its colonial and post-independence history. After Mobutu's fall in 1997, the DRC experienced the devastating First and Second Congo Wars, involving multiple African nations. In response, the UN established MONUC in 1999, which later transitioned to MONUSCO in 2010, with a mandate to protect civilians, support reforms, demobilize fighters, and aid humanitarian efforts. Key achievements include supporting elections, neutralizing rebel groups like M23, and establishing the Force Intervention Brigade in 2013, which weakened armed groups significantly. Despite these successes, challenges such as persistent armed groups, logistical and financial constraints, and inconsistent government cooperation hindered progress. Public frustration grew, leading to protests and calls for UN withdrawal, which the Congolese government sought by 2024. However, the UN extended MONUSCO's mandate until 2025 (Resolution 2765) to continue joint efforts with local forces. The ongoing presence of armed groups is rooted in deep structural issues like weak governance, economic disparities, and historical grievances. Sustainable peace requires a comprehensive approach addressing these underlying causes, emphasizing long-term stability over solely military solutions.

It is on the basis of these findings that the recommendations below are being made in order to improve the security situation in Congo.

1. Promoting sustainable peace in DR Congo requires inclusive national dialogue and governance reforms. With support from the UN and regional partners, the government should engage all ethnic, social

and political groups to address grievances, marginalization, and exclusion. Strengthening institutions, reducing corruption, and improving resource management can build public trust and foster lasting stability.

2. The United Nations should adopt a more comprehensive, multi-dimensional approach to peacekeeping, addressing political, social, security, and economic issues. Mandates should be designed to address deep-seated political, social, security and economic issues while remaining flexible to adapt to changing conditions on the ground. Though such an approach demands more time, resources, and coordination, it provides a stronger and more lasting foundation for peace.

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